

The Kinetic Energy of Relativistic Particles

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Abstract:

This paper has been retracted upon the confirmation of Relativistic Kinetic Energy by Bertozzi's Experiment.

Keywords: Relativity, Classical Mechanics, Hypergeometrical Universe